

CO-FIRING MULTIPLE FUELS IN VOJANY THERMAL POWER PLANT

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Abstract

Rising fuel prices and the steady costs increase of carbon dioxide emissions force the thermal power plants to search for alternative feedstock. Finding a way of cleaner power production is an imperative if a definitive shutdown of ageing coal power plants is to be avoided. Vojany power plant responded to this need a few years ago and started its transformation from a coal power plant to a multi-fuel power source. Positive experiences of coal-wood chips mixture combustion in plant's boilers since 2009 served as a basis for a far more ambitious goal – to gradually replace coal by alternative fuels. Successful tests with solid recovered fuel combustion in 2019 and the permit to use this alternative fuel for power production granted thereafter constituted a breakthrough in the effort to produce cleaner power. Since then, the long-term experiences confirmed the feasibility of plant's operation as multi-fuel power source. In this contribution, the underlying operation experiences are discussed, and basic performance figures are provided, highlighting the plant's transformation as an example that could inspire other power plants in the region to proceed likewise.

Introduction

The issue of ageing fossil power plant fleet in Central and Eastern Europe deserves a sustainable and economically feasible solution¹. Their retirement option is not good news for the power grid stability, as they serve as baseload providers but, at the same time, are flexible enough to support the grid in case of longer lasting imbalances. Repowering of coal power plant with natural gas-based technologies might prolong their lifetime but does not solve the issue of greenhouse gases emissions as natural gas is perceived only as a transition fuel, though substantially cleaner than coal or oil^{2,3}. Additional incentive supporting repowering and reconstruction projects, including those to enrich fuel mix with alternative fuels is related to public health and environmental impacts of power generation and the associated costs that are not internalized (are not part of electricity market price)⁴. Those costs are termed externalities and can amount to tens of €/MWh⁵. Recent studies quantified externalities related to power production from gas to 10 to 20 €/MWh while those resulting from power production from coal amounted to over 40 €/MWh^{6,7}.

Waste management in Central Europe region differs significantly country by country⁸. In Slovakia, landfilling is still the most prominent way of dealing with waste and substantial effort has to be developed to reach a significant cut in it, complying with the European Union regulations⁹. Landfilled waste releases methane, which is a by far more intense greenhouse gas than carbon dioxide. Even if captured and used for power and heat production, it is too diluted to be economically feasible and represents mostly a way how to convert methane to a less harmful gas (carbon dioxide). Waste processing capacities in Slovakia are underdeveloped, with only two large municipal waste incineration plants being in operation¹⁰. At the same time, several hundred thousand tons per annum of processed and sorted waste are used in clinker and cement plants in Slovakia, the majority of which has to be supplied from other countries.

Both the issue of ageing power plant and the untapped potential for local fuel source has prompted Slovenské elektrárne, a.s., the Vojany thermal power plant owner, to test refuse-derived fuel as a possible coal replacement in future. The aim of this study is to analyze the power plant operation before and after fuel mix change, to analyze fuel parameters and to assess the feasibility of refuse-derived fuel inclusion in and of biomass share increase in the power plant fuel mix from technical, energy, economic and environmental points of view.

Materials and methods

Vojany thermal power plant is located in Eastern Slovakia. It is a subcritical coal power plant with an installed power output of 2x110 MW. It was designed to combust black coal from Russia and Ukraine as there are no black coal seam in Slovakia. Natural gas serves only during power boiler start-ups and for stabilization of combustion process. Since 2009 biomass was included in the fuel mix but with a comparatively low share on fuel energy input (a few %).

Tables I and II sum up the basic power plant operation parameters in the period 2016 to 2020. Total power production exceeded 400, even 600 GWh per year till 2018 and then it gradually decreased to 314 GWh per year in 2019 and even to less than 75 GWh per year in 2020. This resulted from decreased amount of combusted coal, while co-combusted biomass amount increased and that of natural gas did not vary too significantly. Refuse-derived fuel (RDF) was tested as alternative feedstock for power generation in 2019 and 2020 but its share on total annual fuel energy input was low.

Table I

Basic operation parameters of Vojany thermal power plant

Parameter/year	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Net power generated from alternative feedstock, GWh	5.89	20.99	21.64	20.67	12.91
Total net power generated, GWh	431.44	607.08	693.94	313.70	74.20
Average net output per block when in service, MW	61.86	66.49	60.22	61.90	57.20

Table II

Fuel balance of Vojany thermal power plant

Fuel type/year	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Biomass (tons)	6,035	20,974	20,263	20,666	12,906
RDF (tons)	-	-	-	1,550	4,900
Coal, 10 ³ tons	208	282	331	151	33
Natural gas, 10 ³ m ³	539	833	625	404	349

Table III

Relative fuel prices per GJ lower heating value (coal = 100 %)

Fuel type/year	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Biomass	147	116	98	119	104
RDF	-	-	-	40	31
Natural gas	1285	654	705	444	376

Data in Table III elucidate the economic incentives for such power plant operation. Apart from CO₂ costs that increased significantly over the analyzed period, coal became an expensive fuel in comparison with biomass or with RDF. Given the low power prices, power production from coal became infeasible and plant managers faced the option either to shut the plant down or seek for alternative fuels that would be more sustainable. RDF price, together with reasonable biomass content in it, made it a promising candidate to be tested for longer operation in co-combustion mode with coal and biomass. Data from conducted tests are analyzed in Results and discussion section.

To complete the description of the situation, it must be stated that Slovenské elektrárne, a.s. operate one more thermal power plant, located in Upper Nitra region in Western Slovakia. This power plant fires local brown coal. Coal mining in the region will stop at the end of 2022 and this power plant will retire consecutively.

Results and discussion

Table IV provides insight into several quality parameters of fuels forming the Vojany power plant fuel mix. Natural gas is not used during normal operation. Lower heating value of natural gas is by far the highest, followed by coal. Biomass and RDF have lower heating values lower than 20 MJ kg⁻¹, due to their chemical composition. This is partly reflected in carbon content as well. It is interesting to compare CO₂ emissions released by complete combustion of fuels listed in Table IV expressed per mass and per energy unit. Natural gas exhibits the highest CO₂ emissions per mass unit but the lowest ones per energy unit, given its very high calorific value. On the other hand, biomass releases least CO₂ per mass unit, but most of it per energy unit. After CO₂ emissions recalculation giving credit to renewable carbon content in fuels, the highest fossil CO₂ emissions are attributable to coal. CO₂

emissions released by RDF combustion stem partly from its non-renewable constituents and partly from its renewable part; nevertheless, they are much lower than those from coal combustion. This clearly underlines the effort developed by Vojany power plant in phasing coal out and replacing it by fuels with lesser carbon footprint. Comparison of dry stoichiometric flue gas amount per energy unit delivers important findings, too. Biomass, coal and RDF produce approximately the same flue gas amount per energy unit, meaning that the flue gas path in the boiler is loaded with similar flue gas volumetric flow at given boiler thermal output, regardless of fuel fired. Natural gas is used only during boiler start-ups and for stabilization of combustion process, so that the fact, that it forms less flue gas per energy unit has no serious impact on totally produced flue gas.

Table IV

Comparison of individual fuels in recent fuel mix. LHV = lower heating value. * = 6 % vol. O₂ in dry flue gas; @ = 3 % vol. O₂ in dry flue gas

Fuel/average parameter value	LHV, GJ t ⁻¹	Carbon content, % wt.	CO ₂ emissions, t t ⁻¹	CO ₂ emissions kg GJ ⁻¹	Fossil CO ₂ emissions, kg GJ ⁻¹	Dry stoichiometric flue gas, Nm ³ GJ ⁻¹
Biomass (as received)	11.4	37	1.36	119	0	390*
Coal	24.6	58	2.12	86	86	370*
RDF	19.5	35	1.3	67	47	300-400*
Natural gas	48.9	72	2.65	54	54	280@

Recent and planned fuel mix of Vojany power plant is summed up in Table V. The change in combusted fuel amounts is clearly visible, with plant's management striving to phase coal completely out, replacing it with RDF and, partly, by biomass. This is a long-term issue, coupled with several operational tests and with optimizing process conditions for its successful implementation, including an investment in a new, fluid steam boiler with circulating fluid bed. Apart from economic and environmental reasons, current geopolitical situation strongly favors the use of fuels that can be produced locally. What remains somewhat unclear is whether local biomass resources suffice to cover the ambitious plan for 2022. Regarding RDF, its domestic production capacities are underdeveloped at the moment and significant part of the fuel must be transported over longer distance. It makes sense to support and create local RDF production capacities to stabilize its share in Vojany fuel mix on one hand and to boost circular economy in the region on the other one.

Table V

Recent and planned fuel mix. * = planned value

Fuel type/year	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022*
Biomass (tons)	20,263	20,666	12,906	30,030	49,643
RDF (tons)	-	1,550	4,900	88,940	150,000
Coal, 10 ³ tons	331	151	33	61.3	0

Table VI

Average concentrations of selected pollutants in dry flue gas

Concentration, mg Nm ⁻³	CO	NO _x	Particulate matter	SO _x
2018	182	63	8.8	167
2019	189	47	6.7	166
2020	161	67	5.6	119
2021	188	62	7.0	147

Data shown in Table VI have to be analysed along with the dry stoichiometric flue gas formation values listed in Table IV. Concentration profiles on individual air pollutants over the years 2018 to 2021 indicate that, regardless of the actual fuel mix, neither have the emission limits been violated, nor has the total amount of released pollutants changes significantly as a result of it. This provides additional justification for enriching the fuel mix with both biomass and RDF. 2020 values fall out of the observed trend. It should, though, be remembered that overall power production fell to a minimum in that year and the share of natural gas on totally combusted fuels was significant – see Table I and II. This was reflected in slightly lower emissions of CO, particulate matter and of SO_x, compared to the corresponding values in the other three years.

Data trends observed in Table VII resemble those in Table VI closely and yield a similar explanation as well. No significant influence of RDF inclusion in and biomass share increase in the fuel mix over years can be observed.

Carbon content in bed ash is below 1 % wt. during the whole period, with the lowest values reached in 2019 and 2020. Fly ash contained approximately the same amount of carbon, except in 2020 which, similarly to the minima in air pollutant in 2020 can be attributed to lower coal share in the fuel mix. As results from Table VI and VII, enrichment of the Vojany fuel mix by RDF and by larger biomass share did neither lead to higher emissions of air pollutants nor to worsened fuel burnout, leading to the conclusion that boiler thermal efficiency did not vary significantly with the fuel mix changes.

Table VII
Average values of carbon content in ash

Carbon content, % wt.	Bed ash	Fly ash
2018	0.53	7.60
2019	0.21	7.04
2020	0.35	3.13
2021	0.77	6.65

Additional information from Vojany power plant include the fact that produced steam parameters were invariant to changes in fuel mix, providing additional proof that fuel mix enrichment by RDF and by larger biomass share is feasible both from technical, energy and environmental point of view. Furthermore, fuel cost relations indicated in Table III clearly exhibit the trend of coal becoming a too expensive fuel which becomes even more obvious if CO₂ costs were added to fuel costs. Phasing coal out of the fuel mix is thus perceived as the only option how to avoid the power plant retirement and, at the same time, RDF is deemed as a suitable replacement for coal both from quality, costs and availability point of view.

Refuse-derived fuel is produced in waste management plants and is rich in paper and plastic wastes; in addition, it contains some other constituents such as of biomass, textile, and other components^{11,12}. Experiences with its combustion and co-combustion in thermal power plants in Western and Northern Europe are documented in several studies^{13,14}. Besides serving as alternative fuel for heat and power production, it is known to successfully replace fossil fuels in clinker and cement production^{15,16} or in iron and steel industry¹⁷. This provides sufficient evidence that choosing RDF as part of the fuel mix in Vojany power plant might be a good decision.

Conclusion

This contribution analyses the feasibility of fuel mix changes in Vojany thermal power plant resulting from the economic necessity and environmental incentives. Inclusion of refuse-derived fuel in the fuel mix was tested in 2019 and, later, in 2020, followed by its increased share in the fuel mix in 2021. Fuel data analysis yielded that RDF is compatible with other fuels such as coal and biomass and can be co-combusted without serious technical, energy and environmental issues. Although these findings are promising, longer testing is necessary. A successful inclusion of RDF in the fuel mix of Vojany thermal power plant might inspire other ageing power plants in Central and Eastern Europe to consider choosing similar path. A boost in regional circular economy can be anticipated as a result, developing waste processing capacities, lowering waste landfilling share and creating new job opportunities. In addition, stable but flexible power sources will be maintained which will allow to include additional renewable energy (wind, solar) based power sources to be phased in the European power grid without an increased risk of blackout.

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